

ARTS

Estranging Comics

—
Towards a novel comics praxeology

Ilan Manouach

"I just saw something in your little corset, dear."

Aalto University publication series
DOCTORAL THESES 40/2022

Estranging Comics

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Abstract

The industry-wide adoption of digital and network technologies has produced long-lasting and unevenly distributed effects in all the sectors of the comics industry. The globalization of markets and services has profoundly reshaped comics labor. Its effects are economic (the precarization of craftsmanship traditions), social (the rise of entrepreneurial fan culture and the consolidation of increasingly diversified communities with novel forms of amateur and semi-professional activity), technical (the introduction of digital tools for the distribution, the archival and retrieval of media artefacts) and aesthetic (the gradual integration in the production pipeline of AI and synthetic media). As is demonstrated by the recent emergence of radical forms of experimentation documented in the Conceptual Comics media collections of Ubuweb and Monoskop, comic artists are often able to leverage the dependencies of the ever-growing network infrastructure of the comics industry. Nevertheless, these disruptions foreground an epistemic crisis in the understanding of contemporary comics, both in academia and in more traditionally established professional spheres.

This thesis embraces an attitude of productive estrangement towards the medium's forms, material qualities and operations, and constructs comics as a "contemporary object". According to philosopher Anne-Françoise Schmid, a contemporary object is an extra-disciplinary entity that is massively distributed in space and time. Understanding such an object depends on the increasingly aggregate nature of knowledge production and dissemination in the computational age. Both in theory, with a series of papers in peer-review journals, and in artistic practice, by way of published comics and commissioned curatorial projects, this thesis examines the mutations of the comics ecology as an expansion of the scope of knowledge. It embraces the cumulative impact of digital transformation and articulates a novel comics praxeology predicated on two conditions. First, the thesis appeals for a systematic exploration of comics outside of narrow media purviews, the implicitly disciplinary conceptions, and the dominant historical perspectives in Comics Studies. It aims to develop a conception that embraces a rigorous application of a non-hegemonic interdisciplinarity in comics research. Second, and most importantly, the thesis argues for the expansion of operational agency on the part of comics professionals. This agency is described as a heightened contextual appreciation of the industry's infrastructural backend, an awareness of its imbricated institutions and a diversification of the professional toolbox. I argue that a novel comics praxeology is a necessary attribute in order to embrace future, speculative, unclaimed or hitherto impossible forms in comics expression.

Introduction
*Towards a novel
comics praxeology*

Introduction

Comics are variously framed as an industry, a genre, an artistic medium, a system of visual/narrative communication, a set of traditions in craftsmanship, different community subcultures, a form of entertainment and an educational tool. But despite the definitional exuberance in academic research around comics, and the apparent multiplicity in the ways we understand and use comics in everyday life, the recent emergence of radical forms of experimentation in artistic practices has both challenged our assumptions about the medium's modes of address, and pointed to the limitations of the given analytical tools in Comics Studies. Contemporary comics are technical objects whose operational intensity is considerably shaped by the comics industry's infrastructure and the crossings and multiplications of information flows. In that regard, the emergence of radical artistic practices is predicated on the epistemological mutations brought forward by the increasingly aggregate nature of knowledge production and dissemination of our computational age that has an immediate effect on the ways we consume, disseminate and archive media content.

This dissertation argues for an attitude of constructive estrangement towards comics and presents both theoretical and practical/artistic perspectives on the constitution of comics as a highly malleable contemporary object of reflection. Throughout this introduction, I argue that a practiced estrangement is at the crux of understanding contemporary comics praxeology. More precisely, the introduction to my dissertation follows the theoretical intuitions of Generic Epistemology and its ethos for disciplinary co-habitation. It argues for the construction of a generic space of research where the production of new insights does not depend on any established models in the field or any single methods of research. Instead, it is predicated on genuine mechanisms of disciplinary cohabitation where researchers and artists practice epistemic estrangement by disentangling objects from their most well-known concepts in order to start accounting for future, speculative, unclaimed or impossible forms of comics art.

Vignette 1: Zou Luoyang, a comics artist inspired by the emerging interdisciplinary sub-field that explores the wider role of waste in society and culture, distributes his self-published zine exclusively in dumpsters. His artistic practice thematizes the lack of cultural respectability for comics, and points to the ecological footprint in greenhouse gas emissions related to the disposability of printed matter. (Comics X Discard Studies)

Vignette 2: A self-proclaimed hoarder, Inès Chuquet, acquires wholesale batches of unsold comic books and examines, as part of her artistic research, the different varieties of micro-climatic cultivations of mould and mildew that grow on castaway commodities. Her practices frame comics artefacts as organic matter. (Comics X Microbiology)

Vignette 3: As comics are no longer exclusively understood as a visual medium, the artist-initiated Shapereader project addresses people with visual disabilities through a free-floating repertoire of tactile geometric symbols that can be iteratively attributed different meanings according to a narrative's demands. (Comics X Disability Studies)

These works are some examples from the experimental comics archive I curated on behalf of Ubuweb, one of the largest online media collections of avant-garde art. The archive documents a growing body of works, and explores new forms of experimentation in the field of contemporary comics as a material basis for artistic innovation. Over the last ten years, comics workers have been pushing the comics medium into uncharted territories. Originating from an international, highly diversified socio-demographic class of comics artists, collectives and publishing initiatives, contemporary comics are often situated far from the global epicenters of comic book production, and are located at the crossroads of different media, practices and sensibilities. The aforementioned vignettes are symptomatic of the political, social and aesthetic mutations that are currently shaping the comics industry. Presently, a polarity is developing between the conventional image of what is a comic and what comics artists and readers are supposed to be doing, and, on the other hand, different artistic conceptions that resist prevailing critical analysis. I have loosely filed these resistant conceptions under the generic term “conceptual comics” (see Chapter 1, “Outlining Conceptual Practices in Comics”).

Looming below the surface of this dichotomy, is a sense of a radical evolution in the forms and modes of address that take place in the comics medium, and which seems to run counter to the mainstream acceptance of comics as a craft, a minor artform or a literary subgenre. This evolution does not always occur as a series of absolutely logical and incremental changes, nor is it only a direct outcome of increasingly networked and digital affordances. As yet, the evolving politics of the comics medium has no critical vocabulary so necessary for the defense of these new works, nor for that matter, a rigorous and systemic interdisciplinary approach that can account for this productive

effervescence. One reason might be the exceptional diversity in the constituency of these artists. They generally come from diverse professional backgrounds removed from art contexts and often involving technical training, specialized knowledge and experience in working across disciplines. Their multi-disciplinary skills are rarely the products of a consistent educational program. The capacities they developed for the production of their works are usually the results of individual and idiosyncratic choices.

Nevertheless, what conceptual comics artists have in common is an understanding of comics that moves beyond disciplinary boundaries or formal and compartmental media terminologies. For these artists, most of whom are “post-digital” natives, comics is more than a vehicle of individual artistic expression developed through a cultivated familiarity with the medium’s traditional canons or any technical accomplishment in craft. On the contrary, conceptual comics distance themselves from an established, conventional view of craftsmanship and embrace the comics industry’s *operational* and *technical* intensity, as the products of an industrial expression. Some of these works, such as the early Stefano Tamburini’s *Snake Agent from 1984*, with his creative use of Xerox technologies, implicitly echo the avant-garde situationist artist Asger Jorn and his reflection on the benefits and challenges of automation: “It is up to us whether standardization opens up more interesting realms of experience than it closes” (Jorn 1957). These words become a rallying cry that celebrates contemporary comics as a vast terrain of industrial experimentation for the production of works that, in other sectors of contemporary research and practice, might be too expensive, too risky, very slow or simply highly dependent on institutional support, to initiate. The medium’s low-risk deployment, its scarce financial resources, but also its community support mechanisms, rather than constituting here the medium’s limitations as it has often been theorized, are deployed as necessary conditions for the formation of a new industrial expression. Conceptual comics become a Petri dish for tackling larger ideas in politics, technologies and ethics. As the Conceptual Comics Archive demonstrates, the documented works have intensified the decompartmentalization of the comics medium, and by the same token, have pointed to the limitations of the various dominant analytical tools that have been traditionally mobilized in Comics Studies.

Epistemological Crisis

Conceptual comics, along with other forms of experimentation in the medium, they pose

a challenge to the available disciplinary methods that are popular in comics research. An important epistemological question therefore arises: can Comics Studies account for the variety of contemporary forms and insights produced by an increasingly diversified class of comics professionals? Or, more regrettably, is comics research limited to defining and characterizing comics through traits extracted from past histories, and only suffice in operating marginal displacements by continuously adding new ones as they emerge? At the crossroads of institutional, educational and commercial establishments, comics artworks have the potential to play out multiple infrastructural interests. The question of whether these interests might be integrated into broader strategies with far-ranging impacts on the comics industry, is tied to how we understand the production of new insights in comics, and what futures we are able to construct from these insights.

The fact that there is little to no scholarly writing about the individual works from the conceptual comics collection of the Ubuweb archive, points to a relative failure of comics academia, and to the current frames of knowledge that are still dominant in comics research. The production and understanding of novelty in the comics medium, as demonstrated by these works and other similar artistic practices, should no longer depend on the implicit disciplinary conceptions, the existing critical apparatuses and the specific historical perspectives of Comics Studies. Strands of comparative literature analysis or narratology, might have been productive in the understanding of comics in the past. Unfortunately, these tools can no longer deliver meaningful theorizations with regard to the increasing heterogeneity of forms, histories, communities and technologies that are shaping, and have been shaped by the comics industry.

Comics Studies therefore, needs to start considering the multitude of practices in comics by encompassing objects that are not constituted yet as facts or fully blown practices, such as in the work of Zou Louoyang, nor can they be integrated within narratives of historical continuity of the medium, like in the Shapereader project. The current diversity overwhelms the usual disciplinary frameworks, be it semiotic, narratological, geographical or historical. New insights in comics art, demonstrate the need for an external, epistemological space that is situated outside the purview of Comics Studies, or at the crossroads of multiple research fields. Instead of trying to grasp and fix comics objects, by reducing them to some structural, essential components (diegesis, imagetext constructions, craftsmanship), I argue on the contrary, what is required is an estrangement of comics, opening them up to simultaneous overlapping

perspectives. This epistemological space should be one of rigorous disciplinary cohabitation and should embrace the proliferation of knowledge production mechanisms without implementing any single hegemonic approach. A rigorous interdisciplinarity, consisting of multiple complimentary models and a plurality of epistemologies would rightly reflect the aggregate compositional process of knowledge production in our computational age.

This thesis argues for an attitude in comics research that is based on working between disciplines. My doctoral research consists of both scholarly publications published in peer-reviewed journals and artistic components including my own comic book projects produced with different publishing partners as well as curatorial work that I conducted with various institutional affiliations. The following assumption informs my understanding of a contemporary comics praxeology: the production of knowledge in comics research takes place in an increasingly media-rich and informationally dense environment. Most professional areas of expertise in the industry of comics require an aggregate approach to knowledge, a multiplicity of epistemic regimes and the exploration of extra-disciplinary territories. Echoing Francois Laruelle's urge to "make a tabula rasa of the future" (Laruelle 2012), the epistemic liberation in working between disciplines in comics research, contributes to more than simply revealing hidden intersections of research fields; working between disciplines has an operational constructive intensity similar to what Laruelle calls "futurity", defined as a specific kind of relation to the future that is not tied to the past, neither proceeds through cycles of constant revolutions.

New insights, past ties

In her 1995 essay "On Contemporary Objects", Anne-Françoise Schmid questions the production of new insights in the sciences, but this could be applicable in other research domains. According to Schmid, disciplinary knowledge procedures condition our ideas of contemporaneity. Disciplines structure our recognition of new observations by instituting and preserving discursive mechanisms of historical continuity. This continuity is effectively summoned only when new observations can relate to already established paradigms, either through well-rehearsed forms of dialectical opposition (such as in the paradigm shift) or through complementarity (the incremental additions to existing knowledge). Contrastingly, when classical theories of epistemology cannot account

for “the multiplicity of contemporary manifestations and methods of science” (Schmid 2015), the accumulated knowledge in a scientific field operates with an inhibiting drive; objects that sit uneasily between established categories, or objects that resist totalization by aforementioned precepts of a historical continuity, fail to be integrated within the framework of existing theories and histories. In Comics Studies, the dialectical theorization in the evolution of forms in comics is still the dominant tool mobilized in the understanding of novelty. I would like to demonstrate that novelty cannot rely on the narrow confines of a single discipline nor on its normative mechanisms of historical continuity. I would like to illustrate the limitations of a simple dialectical model in the production of new insights using as an example the resurgence of painterly aesthetics that defined the Belgian independent comics scene in the 2000s.

The popularity of a *visual* experimentation in comics was heralded in Belgian art schools as the most “promising” direction for an “artistic” approach in the medium. Both in the Ecole Supérieure des Arts de St.Luc (ESA) where I did my BFA in the late 1990s, and the Ecole de Recherche Graphique (ERG), comics students were expected to experiment with comics in the same way painters experimented with their medium. They were called to expand their comics craft techniques with scribbling, stains, impasto and collage, redefine the formats beyond those imposed by industrial reproduction with the introduction of large canvases, floor painting or the inclusion of non-reproducible three-dimensional objects, and activate modes of display from exhibition making, by presenting their work as unique pieces hung on walls. This was a way for many of my colleagues, and myself, as a young aspiring comics artist, to embrace various forms of gestural “painterly” experimentation; this was, after all, the quasi-canonical paradigm of artistic expression in the general sensibility that radically contrasted with the laborious attitude of comics artists on their desk. The production of non-multiples was more than a deliberate aesthetic choice for students. It was a position that supposedly opposed the medium’s “inherent” reproducibility, and a direct repudiation of Belgium’s very own mainstream comics tradition largely consisting of the international commercial success of *ligne claire*¹ aesthetics.

1. *Ligne claire*, a term coined by Joost Swarte in 1977, defines a style of drawing that was pioneered by the artist Hergé, the author of *Tintin*. The technique is characterized by the use of clear black lines with the same width, strong spot colours, no gradients and no textural hatching for representing variations in shadows. The style is also recognisable by the contrasting depiction of cartoonish characters against more realistic backgrounds, and by its overall flat aspect granting equal amount of attention and focus to human figures and to the backdrop.

Assuming a dialectical opposition to the dominant paradigm, that construed comics as an industrial product defined by prevailing market considerations, the educational establishments, the aspiring comics/painters students, a few comics publishers such as the Brussels-based Frémok² (ex-Fréon) and La Cinquième Couche,³ but also public funding bodies, ended up effecting an overall conservative gesture as visual, and painterly experimentation in comics was in retrospect a class statement. It seemed to be an opportunity for its practitioners to elevate comics craft in the cultural sector by addressing collectors and gallerists rather than readers and publishers, by assigning prices on original works rather than relying on industry practices for book sales, and by marginally expanding graphic and visual arts canons in art history instead of mobilizing the comics industry's very own affordances.

In hindsight, painterly comics were the product of a discipline's narrow understanding of historical continuity and not the oppositional force to the existing aesthetic traditions. Both a misguided opportunity and failed entry in the art market, exclusively occupied as it was, and as far as original comics plates were concerned, with works that had already accumulated the value of heritage, painterly aesthetics ended up confirming the irrelevance and the marginality of comics practices in the larger artistic outlooks. Painterly comics reinforced the stereotype of a milieu and a posture that was desperate for formal respectability but, through the tunnel vision of a narrow dialectical opposition, comics were once again positioned behind a rapidly moving art industry and an already decadent gallery art market. Not unlike the commercial and mainstream comics they "dialectically" opposed, contemporary painterly comics were reified as a dominantly *visual* artistic enterprise.

How did something that looked and felt like a shift in the forms and modes of address in the medium, end up perpetuating a stereotype according to which comics is a parochial, campy craft whose legitimacy can only be predicated on conventional and outdated formats (canvases hung on walls in museum exhibitions)? A discipline's dialectical or complementary evolutionary views of ideas and forms is not justification for the production of new insights. Artistic productions that are tied to single disciplinary formations, with established frameworks of what constitutes a work and what should be

2. Frémok (FRMK) is a Franco-Belgian comics publishing house, that was formed by the union of the former publishers Amok (France) and Fréon (Belgium). <https://www.fremok.org/>

3. La Cinquième Couche, also known as 5c, is an independent Belgian publishing house based in Brussels, structured into a publishing house in 1999 and which publishes mainly experimental comics. <https://5c.be/>

the defining features of an object or a practice, fail to reflect that novelty is increasingly relying on the aggregate production of knowledge that no single discipline, or their linear oppositional historicities can produce.

In a recent lecture informed by Schmid's insights, writer and Urbanomic publisher Robin Mackay suggests that working between disciplines has important political implications not only in the scientific domains but in most objects of contemporary study. The limitations of single disciplinary perspectives, based on historical divisions of labour have to be replaced with new epistemological models of knowledge production where "theoretical, speculative, and historical approaches of the humanities cross over with the empirical and systematic investigations of the sciences" (Mackay 2016). After all, the comics industry is far from being a unitary field of operation. Comics making is an entanglement of commercial, artistic and technical ambitions that is reflected in the historically contingent assortment of roles that define comics professionals. Most comics artists are often highly networked and media-savvy individuals who operate on a freelance basis with no steady affiliations with publishers or other institutions. They have learned to organize their time around a patchwork of fragmented schedules of day job obligations, documentation, reading, research and community work, only part of which could be classified as artistic commissions. From feeding a DeviantArt account with "relatable" comics and reviewing the latest *dōjinshi*,⁴ to setting up a mail-order for a serialised xerox zine and selling original art on Behance, the lives of comics professionals are composed by multiple social activities distributed across various social and economic levels.

I argue that the "weakness of the field's institutional footing" (Hatfield 2010) and the lack of affiliations with cultural establishments that produce the necessary social fabrics regulating financial activity in the arts, do not necessarily constitute a drawback for the comics industry; nor is the medium's general ambivalent positioning in relation to official art history and its canonical criteria of cultural legitimacy. On the contrary, I believe that these conditions induce forms of social relationships, research methods and a certain epistemic standpoint towards plurality in the production and organization of knowledge, that is indeed industry-specific. In other words, it is because, and not despite of their marginal position in the cultural spectrum, that comics allow for specific affordances and operational modalities: the comics industry is construed in this

4. *Dōjinshi* is the Japanese term for describing the self-published, mostly derivative works of existing works of fan-fiction in manga.

perspective as a mediating environment for the production and the distribution of dense, multifaceted contemporary objects depending on particular forms of interdisciplinary labor disseminated in multiple time and space zones. Comics can no longer be assumed as known objects; they require instead the emergence of a novel epistemological space that should take seriously a non-hegemonic disciplinary concurrence.

Comics epistemology

Analytical tools, methods and disciplines are not neutral or ahistorical. Scientific disciplines can be dated and traced back to the strong historical antecedents in the nineteenth century's specialisms. Knowledge production was contingent on the agreed delimitations of the field of a research project, whose role was to articulate all the heterogeneous aspects of an inquiry. A field's institutional consistency was mostly formed through the proceedings of scientific societies that established a certain theoretical unity legitimizing only a specific type of hypotheses, accepting only certain types of evidence through best practices of chains of measurements, observations and experiments. Disciplines generally enforced ideas of the very nature of a scientific problem. Through the works of Michel Foucault, the understanding of disciplines was broadened with important epistemic and institutional consequences which reflected the political and social upheavals of his time. Disciplines previously defined as clearly delimited, forged on well-determined practices, and only capable of specific analogies, were theorized in Foucault's work as social historical constructions. As such, they had the ability to positively constitute objects through sets of rules, habits and productions of enunciations that necessarily involved a convergence of knowledge practices and power relations. In the work of Foucault and in many of his contemporaries, knowledge production was increasingly purged from any assumptions of a detached, disinterested inquiry. Disciplines were therefore increasingly construed as systems of situated knowledge and were further denaturalized in their capacity to construct, and enforce specific views of realities.

The complexities of competing disciplinary perspectives in the understanding of a work, and the way institutional contexts are played out in the preservation or refutation of dominant discursive interpretations can be demonstrated in recent theoretical attempts to revisit canonical works of comics in Comics Studies. In many cases, the understanding of some established works of comics, has been traditionally dominated by outdated

strands of structural narratology, visual culture studies or film theory. Approaching them with a variety of theoretical tools and methods, outside of the canonical apparatuses of Comics Studies, reveals how disciplinary perspectives are both fragile, ephemeral and tied to individual, embodied and historical knowledge mechanisms. An illustration can be found in the simultaneous erosion of classical narratological/semiotic analyses in the genre of superhero comics, and the recent scholarly emergence of approaching the same comics with an abundance of perspectives: disability studies (Alaniz 2014), queer theory (Fawaz 2016), cognitive neuroscience (Cohn 2017), third-wave feminism (Curtis 2017) and post-human body representations (Jeffery 2016), to name just a few. Disciplinary cohabitation is predicated on dynamic cartographies of knowledge production and the confluence of multiple disciplines. Institutional bodies and research interests have their own specific political implications. The pluralization of different hypotheses, practices and disciplines is not simply a prerogative for a contemporary comics praxeology, but a shift “from a critique of truths to the construction of objects” (Schmid and Hatchuel 2014), that allows for engagement with the multiple becomings of comics.

A pluralization of overlapping, non-competing perspectives is also at the heart of comics experimentation and contemporary conceptual practices. The comics industry is a network that consists of a multitude of legal, institutional, economic, political and personal bodies whose speed, direction of movement and overlapping temporalities are shaped by infrastructural affordances. Kenneth Goldsmith intuited that “conceptual writing or uncreative writing is a poetics of the moment, fusing the avant-garde impulses of the last century with the technologies of the present” (Goldsmith 2008). Always co-terminal with technological innovationism, the comics industry proves that “separating publishing from technology is impossible” (Bhaskar 2013). Judging from the diversity and proliferation of conceptual practices in comics and the novel use of archive, production and distribution technologies, one can argue that conditions are ripe for the formation of a genuine interdisciplinarity in the comics infrastructure.

The comics industry is an infrastructure

Speculations about the growing role of automation in artistic production have been a consistent trope in modern and contemporary art debates throughout the twentieth century, and into the twenty-first. The early forerunner exhibition “Machine Art”, curated by Alfred H. Barr Jr. and Philip Johnson in 1934 at the Museum of Modern Art

in New York provocatively put on display items such as typewriter carriage springs, a toaster and a cash register. The exhibition claimed for industrially produced objects that were deemed to be purely functional an aesthetic appreciation equally intense to the one reserved for works of art. Described by Philip Johnson as an “anti-handcraft show” (Zane 1991:32), the exhibition significantly contributed to the expansion of the art collection’s museographical scope, and to a quasi-canonical application of an equal aesthetic scale for art and industrial objects. The show, but also the discussions that it provoked, contributed gradually to the erosion in the humanities of “a conception of technology in which technics is pitched against the human” (Broeckmann 2019), and many years later, this legacy is now clearly part of the general sensibility: a series of sensationalist contemporary shows in important museums worldwide explores the latest creative developments in machine learning and examines how artists can deploy technologies in prescient ways.⁵ These manifestations are no longer perceived as provocative, but as a part of the natural expansion of an ever-growing artistic toolbox. While the conceptual power of machines has shaped the human imagination and found expression in humanity’s rituals, languages and social organization since ancient and prehistoric times, it is only recently that the fiction of quasi-autonomous technical systems is celebrated and thematized to such an extent in the artistic imaginary.

Comics, on the other hand, have been symbiotically expanding from their early beginnings, with the infrastructural development of printing, distribution, communication and media technologies. Since the earliest reproductions, the most auteurist comics, unlike works in other fields of visual culture, could hardly be seen as the figments of a single artistic genius. Their production depended on an array of different professionals and skills. Both formally and conceptually, comics have foregrounded from a technical and economic point of view, important notions of efficiency, marginal utility and computability. Comics are the products of an operative architecture, unfolding sequentially and built from discrete instructions like the stages of a recipe. They are scripted, written, pencilled, inked, coloured, lettered, edited, lithographed, printed, marketed, distributed, sold, collected, archived, digitized, shredded and recycled into pulp.

5. Some of which: “I am here to learn: On Machinic Interpretations of the World” (Frankfurter Kunstverein, 2018), “Machines Are Not Alone: A Machinic Trilogy” (Chronus Art Center, Shanghai, 2018), “Entangled Realities: Living with Artificial Intelligence” (House of Electronic Arts, Basel, 2019), “AI: More Than Human” (Barbican Centre, London, 2019) and “The Work of Art in the Age of Artificial Intelligence” (Victoria and Albert Museum, London, 2018).

Comics are the direct output of an industrial processes of completion based on instituted sets of standardization practices that are deeply embedded in the ways we understand and consume comics, that have become essential features for the conceptualization of artistic practices in the medium. As commodities and disposable goods, comics have been in constant dialogue with the existing consumer technologies that have shaped the medium's forms, modes of address, the composition of its communities and the medium's relation to institutional memory. As objects of sustained attention in art education, comics syllabi are infused with a variety of educational material that goes beyond what can be narrowly defined as artistic: technical knowledge(s), industry's best practices, basics of Intellectual Property law, marketing strategies for self-publishing, digital promotion and career planning. For example, the Center of Cartoon Studies in White River Junction, intensifies this tendency in its educational program. "Applied cartooning", the art of professional flexibility in technically and artistically responding to different job openings, shows how comics education encompasses a multitude of skills beyond the narrow remit of printed comics such as comics journalism, infographics, "graphic facilitation" and advertisement storyboarding.

Comics are situated in a dense information economy and each step in the artistic process is technologically mediated and heavily coded: from the industrial adoption of the patented Ben Day photoengraving technique as a *conversion* tool for color separation in printing technologies and the *optimal* allocation of space for cartoons and daily strips in early newspapers, to the industry's complex *logistics* funnelled through global distribution sinews, transatlantic containers, warehouses and data centers, comics can be described as *technical/computational* objects. The all-encompassing influence of technological advancements has a continuous profound impact on the ways we produce and consume comics. Nevertheless, the technological coevolution takes place in the industry's highly striated space, operating under the conflicting interests of market forces and legal, commercial, historical and academic institutions.

Situated at the vanguard of capitalism, the infrastructure of the publishing industries has always operated as a disruptive force in the knowledge economy, the copyright establishment and the application and enforcement of patent laws, and most importantly with tangible effects to their very own professional constituency. One needs only examine the consolidation of US retail distribution services in the 1980s and the massively digitized operations of logistics and global supply chains in the twenty-first

century, to get a sense of the comics industry's very own vibrant topologies.

In order to understand better how the conceptualization of the comics industry as a hybrid object-human networked activity, can allow, or deter, specific artistic practices, the work of sociologist Susan Leigh Star can be particularly helpful. Her research focused on the informational infrastructures of modern societies and discerns nine defining characteristics in the concept of the infrastructure as a system of substrates: Infrastructures are large scale technical systems that are often *embedded* in other structures and social situations, making their operational aspects hardly discernible to external observation. Infrastructures are complex, multi-layered formations that are built and depend on an *installed base* of sunk capital and whose maintenance often occurs in *modular increments*. Infrastructures *embody* standards, technical specifications and hidden mechanisms, but at the same time they are present as *transparent*, ready to use technical configurations that don't need to be reinvented every time they are called upon. Their operational regimes are usually *linked* to conventions of practices that have been developed by communities of users. Infrastructures are often *learned* and for that matter, they are also taken for granted by a community's "usership". Finally, infrastructures tend to develop their own *temporalities* and modes of *spatial reach*. As highly contextual and relational objects where "one person's infrastructure is another's topic, or difficulty" (Leigh Star 1999), infrastructures become naturalized, invisible and resurface in our consciousness only upon *breakdown*.

With the advent of the Internet and network technologies, the infrastructural dynamics of the comics industry are greatly magnified. For instance, the international emergence of global communities of comics professionals has not only provincialized the few global epicentres of comics production, but also contributed to overruling an array of professionals that once were key agents of the industry. The disruptive and technologically mediated effects of networked affordances can be examined, for instance, through the rising entrepreneurial fan culture and the emergence of independent, interconnected and globally distributed communities of "scanlators".

Scanlating is a portmanteau that describes the unsolicited work of comics fans who buy, scan, translate (usually to English) and distribute online and for free, their favorite manga series. Catering to the needs of a western readership that is thirsty for works that haven't yet been licensed for foreign distribution, and whose "radar" moves faster than the acquisitions of western publishing conglomerates, scanlators operate under what is

called a “gentleman’s agreement” (Pink 2007) where “the redistribution of scanlated manga takes place without explicit approval or material support from the original manga publishers” (Manovich et al. 2011). The unsolicited activity is often strategically allowed by the original publishers as a safe breakthrough in western markets. Scanlating communities operate an entire digital infrastructure, with its marketplace, its online repositories and its very own digital app ecosystem. A “multitude of freely available scans are downloaded in the millions” (Ratti 2013) through media repositories such as MangaReader that consist of the backbone of community engagement in the scanlations communities. These websites are aggregators that often supersede by a large magnitude the existing official and corporate efforts to encourage community engagement, but in reality they are not very different from existing shadow libraries such as *aaaargh* or *Monoskop*. Subscribed users are invited to review their favorite manga series, exchange ideas in adjacent specialized fora and make requests for missing entries. Visitors can also make use of a custom-made crawler, an indexing tool that covers multiple repositories and offers a comprehensive RSS feed to thousands of available scanlated series.

Scanlations also have their own p2p sharing websites and their own legacy file extensions: *cbr* and *cbz* are hybrid file formats, executable by special manga-reader mobile apps and are used for storing and displaying comic books. Besides making a name for themselves or for the highly competitive collectives they represent, scanlators find ways to monetize their work. The downloaded files come often with advertisements, paid editorials, promotional coupons, and any other tried way to commodify the attention of a very large readership. As demonstrated by this quick overview, the emergence of digital and network technologies, allows spontaneous communities of fans to develop novel *technical/affective* capacities in accessing, annotating, archiving, disseminating and monetizing digital artefacts of comics, with highly disruptive implications for the entire sections of an industry.

The scanlations effect would have naturally never been possible without the advent of the Internet’s novel affective infrastructures of sharing and the growing discontent with artificial scarcity in the “new environment of textual abundance” (Goldsmith 2010). Comics are highly malleable technical objects that are shaped by and respond to new infrastructural demands. An infrastructural framing of the comics industry and its organizational affordances allows the contemporary comics artist to undertake specific

sets of actions and productive opportunities for intervention. In “Outlining Conceptual Practices in Comics”, I reflected on Willem Flusser’s historical conceptualization of art making in the information age. While Flusser was explicitly referring to the art of photography, his insights are useful for the comics industry as well. According to the writer, photographers are more like networked performers. They operate with a high degree of abstraction, rely on different layers of information encoding and decoding, and are integral parts of a succession of agents and social institutions that produce their own type of discourses, knowledge(s) and histories. These apparatuses permeate and overdetermine every artefact, every single photograph. These imbricated institutions range from the patent holders of image compression algorithms, to the shareholders of a photographic empire and the military-industrial complex R&D departments developing new technologies. In the example of the scanlation pipeline, each step of the entire chain of labor, from the distribution to the communication, and from the consumption to the annotation, is reflected in the materiality of the very same digital artefacts: manga books are broken down to individual chapters so that readers are only notified about the latest updates through the available RSS feeds. The chapters come as highly compressed files, industry-specific extensions (cbr), specially packaged for readers with low bandwidth; their design, such as the dimensions, the typography, and the promotional material and advertisements, is responsive to the requirements of mobile devices and commercial reader apps, while advertisement links can be directly opened in the native browser of the reading apps, further allowing the gathering of leads and the monetization of visits.

Related to a similar contextual understanding of media, curator Jack Burnham wrote in *Artforum* in 1968, “we are now in transition from an object-oriented to a systems-oriented culture [where change] emanates not from things, but from the way things are done” (Burnham 1968). These technical affordances pose new challenges to conceptual comics artists who navigate and disentangle the different levels of signification that are encoded in each and every artefact. Eager to find out how an infrastructural approach to comics can be updated in our present time and within an increasingly interconnected, globalized comics industry, I turn to what researcher Victoria Ivanova calls “infrastructural praxis”.

Infrastructural praxis is the artistic practice that prioritizes engagement and actions allowed, or afforded by the operational backend: the technical-economic scaffolding that “has the potential to shape the operational domains of other fields (such as)

relationships with other systemic conditions globalization, finance, and the liberal values underwriting human rights regimes” (Ivanova 2019). According to Ivanova, a systemic approach understands how separate demands coalesce and inform each other. The backend traverses the multiple scales and the seemingly separate contexts that constitute the infrastructural space. Infrastructural praxis activates the operational protocols, norms and regulations, the “byproducts of unintended confluences, junctures” and market forces that have been crystallized through repeatability and that have been gradually integrated in the infrastructural connective tissue, often up to the point of being naturalized and taken for granted. Infrastructural praxis and its situated affordances is an opportunity to demote the importance of human-oriented decision making and to explore or to orchestrate situations where infrastructures can be hacked or even stop being operational. Infrastructures, as is demonstrated by Leigh-Starr’s theoretical work and by the example of the scanlation communities, are not only dynamic but are also fragile and volatile. They require intense maintenance and repair. Infrastructural breakdown through erosion or decay is an invitation for hyperawareness; a way to poach holes in the infrastructural tissue and to make their operational capacity, an object of systematic and sustained attention from the perspective of the conceptual comics performer.

The digitization of the production and consumption of comics allows for an unprecedented proliferation of available media. Conceptual comics practices respond to the mutations of the comics ecology as one that is increasingly informationally dense. A recent reviewer of contemporary conceptual poetry historicized this turn in the following words: “If conceptualism tracked the hyperproduction of material objects, neoconceptualism tracks the hyperproduction of services, immaterial goods, finance” (Clover 2014). From the standpoint of the democratization of digital access to media content, Matthew Fuller writes that digital abundance, reflected in the “numerous forms of circulation that exceed, disorder and amplify their capacities as media” (Fuller 2017) does more than just point to the limitations of our conceptual frameworks or disturb our assumptions of what constitutes a book object. Media accumulation is productive in its capacity to expand our relation to memory, to contribute to the awareness of different regimes of attention, to broaden our understanding of the environmental footprint of artistic and publishing production and to rethink the performative aspects of information management as contingent to artistic sensibilities, in terms of what Paul Stephens calls “the poetics of information overload” (Stephens 2015).

Additionally and as creative processes are increasingly shaped by technological affordances, the comics industry is already facing the complex developments in artificial intelligence. The abundance of digitised media content available through third-party groups of comics fans, the increasing convenience of programming language frameworks and machine learning libraries, the secularisation of knowledge through e-learning and plummeting prices in specialised hardware is reaching a critical/inflection point where artificial intelligence will profoundly shape the ways we produce, consume, archive and distribute comics artefacts. An increasingly wide adoption of synthetic media, generative processes and predictive algorithms will not only reconfigure existing readerships and markets, but will ultimately force a radical realignment for the practitioners' artistic ethos and contribute to the formation of new reader sensibilities. As is demonstrated by the twitter bot *The Neural Yorker*, the use of deep learning technologies in comics, powered by multiple models trained on millions of data units whose collection occurs on a variety of different indexing regimes, both thematizes and accelerates the effects of the aggregate nature of knowledge production in a semiocapitalist age.

Comics Interdisciplinarity

As fragmentary observations, theories and experiences fail to cohere in the production of clearly delineated systemic disciplinary knowledge, the contemporary discussion around disciplinary concurrence attains momentum in multiple areas of expertise. The production of contemporary comics relies and depends on multiple infrastructural overlapping temporalities and globally distributed and interconnected labor regimes. How can we account for the production of new insights in comics when comics cannot be contained within single disciplinary approaches? In scientific research, the explicit heterogeneity is typical in extremely large objects, or what philosopher and literary theorist Timothy Morton calls "hyperobjects". These objects of study, such as global warming or radioactive plutonium, are massive, nonlocal entities that transcend human spatiotemporal specificities. They are inter-objective systems, formed through the relations between multiple objects, eliding simple and detached descriptions. They cannot be disentangled from the observer in a conventional epistemological distance. Hyperobjects such as climate change for example are dense, multilayered objects that beg for multiple disciplinary inputs and approaches that go beyond the narrow scientific and managerial existing frameworks (O'Neill 2010). Morton's own writing on hyperobjects exemplifies this attitude, and draws from quantum physics, climate science

and contemporary art among others. Contemporary research is increasingly determined by the scientific need for pluriformalized modelizations and computer simulations that have led to “the coexistence and the co-calculation of a multiplicity of formalisms” (Varenne 2009). The increasing informatization of knowledge and the aggregate nature of its production means that the mobilization of multiple disciplinary perspectives is no longer an exceptional state in the sciences, regarding only the study of hyperobjects. Increasingly, any system manifesting a certain complexity overrides single disciplines and has to be captured in its “interdisciplinary oscillation” (Schmid et al. 2011).

For example, an emerging research field that is co-contemporaneous to comics research is Curatorial Studies. As an emerging area of research, it shares a similar lack in the consistency and solidity of established academic fields. It addresses similar challenges in formulating its foundational narratives, much like Comics Studies. Contemporary curating practices have been gradually shifting away from a professional purview traditionally consisting in the narrow imperatives of exhibition making, towards embracing a diversity in critical practices around visual cultures. As a result, Curatorial Studies started questioning its very own object of research. Jean-Paul Martinon, the co-founder of the Curatorial PhD Program at Goldsmiths, wrote that contemporary curating is a practice that no longer needs to be legitimized by any single institutional discourse (historical, theoretical, socio-cultural or political), and that consequently “can only be taught in fragmentary forms detached from any previous system, including any previously shattered disciplines” (Martinon 2017). New directions in Curatorial Studies tentatively embraced the aggregate nature of knowledge production and this turn, according to the author, means that the traditional demands of professional integrity in the field are revised in order to respond to “the exigency of fragmentation, the imperative of the smithereens”, making curating an important toolbox in the contemporary world.

A similar dynamic is played out in Comics Studies, where there is little agreement about the nature of comics research and “its history, its methods, and the intellectual and institutional goals that will determine its future” (Steirer 2011). One important factor stems determinately from the lack of attachment for Comics Studies to a specific research department nexus. This is due to the lack of scholarly consensus about their media specificity, or in Greenbergian terms, as comics’ very own “unique and proper area of competence”. Described by Aaron Meskin as the “definitional project” (Meskin

2007), the heated debate around “what comics is” is based on a largely modernist assumption about what the defining features are, the expressive possibilities and the modalities of representation in comics, and to what extent an academic consensus should give rise to a normative framework of shared convictions about methods, histories and canons.

Here, it is important to be reminded that all definitional projects, whether they frame comics as a form of literature, an artistic medium, a set of craftsmanship traditions, a multimodal construction, or just a social object, are always pegged to entrenched academic interests that cannot, and do not need to converge. Studies in comics are “scattered across disciplines” (Steirer 2011) and are always produced through the sum and the variety of “backgrounds, traditions and research interests that comics scholars bring in the field” (Woo 2019). Therefore, disciplinary affiliations have an immediate effect on the academic understanding of the medium’s affordances. One could argue that comics is a genuinely interdisciplinary endeavour. Unfortunately, as is demonstrated by the institutional affiliations with Literary Studies for most comics researchers, comics research predominantly exists as a narrowly circumscribed domain due “to the largesse of English departments” (Beaty & Woo 2016). This ends up necessarily prioritizing certain (literary) readings of the medium. For instance, the recent “literary turn” in research (Beaty 2012), expressed through the early writings of Rocco Versaci, Charles Hatfield or Harry Morgan in France, attempts to describe comics based on the medium’s literary premises. The “literary turn” gained increasing traction as the prevailing direction in comics academia. According to Charles Hatfield, the academic study that explores the literary values of contemporary comics works towards the academic legitimization of these works and can be understood as an “incipient attack from within on hidebound ideas of what literature itself is or should be” (Hatfield 2010). Alternatively its purview is to marginally expand the established literary canons, i.e. by highlighting, through the lenses of comparative analysis with more “legitimate” (sic) literary and media genres, the power of character-driven narratives in canonical comic books (Versaci 2007).

As Comics Studies is gradually constituted as a fully-fledged field, with its own journals, conferences and imprints in academic presses, the relation with other academic fields becomes a matter of programmatic concern. Working between disciplines is often portrayed as a trade-off. From Benjamin Woo’s question “what might we gain by

drawing comics studies and media studies into closer alignment?” to Henry Jenkins’s “should the reading comics be disciplined?” and Art Spiegelman’s “faustian deal with culture”, to Bart Beaty’s “do we have to sacrifice too much specificity in order to regard comics as a literary form?”, comics praxeology, and interdisciplinary cohabitation seems to be an eternal compromise haunted by Faustian overtones.

One may wonder nevertheless if performing comparative analysis on graphic novels is really a mark of working across disciplines. It is hard not to agree that the object of comics is predominantly pegged to literary disciplinary perspectives. It’s tempting to read this as a symptom of an irrecoverable gravitational force operating in academic faculties. After all, dedicated journals, conferences and research groups are always originating in specific departments, and address specific constituencies of scholars. Interdisciplinary attributes are often perceived by some researchers as contributing to the fragility of the medium (Troutman 2013), triggering, like in the example of the “literary turn”, hegemonic disciplinary attitudes based on the domination of a single knowledge production mechanism. Whether this mechanism is experiential, theoretical, or tied to conventional disciplinary automatisms, such as the knee-jerk mistrust of images, being “one of the basic ideological moves of literary studies” (Hatfield 2017), the disciplinary ambivalence of comics research is often framed as an institutional liability, and a call to action.

The writer and critic Dale Jacobs notices that the question of interdisciplinarity in comics becomes a matter of articulation begging the following question; how are the constituted fields of comics research (cartooning, librarianship, etc.) supposed to integrate methodologies from other fields such as book history and media studies (Jacobs 2019)? While Jacobs rightly stresses that this is a collective issue that demands sustained attention from the entire community of comics researchers, he glosses over the important political ramifications that come with conventional disciplinary cohabitation and the fact that in comics, interdisciplinarity traditionally seems to come in the “shallowest descriptive sense” (Steirer 2011).

It’s important also to acknowledge, that despite the typologies of different kinds of disciplinary cohabitation that have been put forward, active in one way or another in current comics research and education (Hatfield 2010), knowledge production has a certain relation to futurity that interdisciplinarity hasn’t quite been able to capture yet. A non-explicit injunction to work across disciplines in Comics Studies could be

framed as a structural position against the usual disciplinary urge to reduce research objects to their most obvious features. Unfortunately, following the aforementioned example in Curatorial Studies, there is little academic consensus, mostly justified by the researcher's academic affiliations, about whether disciplinary concurrence should be genuinely embraced.

In his 2010 critical article "Indiscipline, or, The Condition of Comics Studies", Charles Hatfield, echoing an implicit premise on the nature of the field, advised for the development of an intentional interdisciplinary ethos in comics research. Due to "the heterogeneous nature of comics" (Hatfield 2010), Comics Studies, he claimed, is a productive field of academic interest with no cohesive, self-contained disciplinary identity. As an object of inquiry, comics research somehow "has fallen between the cracks", and can only be accessible through the intersection of multiple disciplines. Hatfield justly asserted that research in the field is a challenge to the specialization and the compartmentalization of knowledge production in general. This opportunity should "foster collaboration and collegueship across disciplinary and programmatic boundaries", something that should equally be reflected in a deep restructuring of academic programs, schools and university faculties. In 2017, the situation hasn't considerably changed and Hatfield rehashes and broadens his initial statement. He adds, echoing Jean-Paul Martinot's idea, that Comics Studies, "a liminal field, defined by the unresolved nature of its very object of study" is "a challenge to the very idea of disciplinarity as the academy is used to practising it".

I suggest we take Hatfield's intuition seriously and not just as a tactical opportunity to operate marginal expansions of a canon inside departments of English. The sustained substantial disagreements on the nature of comics within the research community, and the dispersal of comics research in the academic spectrum, are not a mere limitation. The heterogeneity of comics threatens the very same idea of media disciplinarity. Following a similar dynamic in Curatorial Studies but also in other nascent fields of research, liminality could be weaponized in order to prepare the ground for a new epistemological space leading to the abandonment of top-level access modes to knowledge production, as well as the desire to critically and theoretically exhaust any object by reducing it to its basic field properties. A real democracy of disciplines is incompatible with hierarchies of hegemonic disciplinary regimes, such as Comparative Literature, Popular Culture Studies or Film Theory. Comics, when hollowed out from any defining features

pegged to specific academic intensities, become an invitation to rigorously think and mobilize a genuine disciplinary concurrence. It seems therefore increasingly necessary to unstitch comics from traditional media interpretations, disentangle research from the predicaments of the present and focus on the unknown as a structural part of a systematic exploration of comics.

Generic Epistemology

The comics industry is an infrastructure distributed across multiple timescales and geographies that can only be described through the residual traces and inscriptions produced throughout the different layers of meaning signification. Comics infrastructures can be approached through intrinsically aggregate knowledge production mechanisms that follow the hyper-complexity shift in contemporary sciences. New insights in Comics Studies express the need for an epistemological space that is structured neither by the domination of certain disciplines nor by the traditional tension between theory and a certain relation to the real. Generic Epistemology is an epistemology of modelizations. Manifested through the need for multi-agential strategies (Schmid) and simulation and modelization practices (Legay), it responds to and reflects an understanding of knowledge production based on working across disciplines. Initially conceived as a tool of scientific method that can account for the creation of new disciplines in sciences such as quantum biology or computational social science, Generic Epistemology invites us to rethink the proceedings of scientific methods by pointing correspondingly to the insufficiency of unique and singular disciplinary perspectives. By vouching for the framing of a research object as a largely unknown one, Generic Epistemology allows us to elude simple formalizations; the objects' inherent heterogeneity is no longer treated as a marginal predicament but becomes a constituent feature for any meaningful insight.

Without demoting the historical importance of individual disciplines, Generic Epistemology brings forward an integrative approach to knowledge that is not predicated on any specific doctrinal system, the hierarchical relations of different disciplines, nor on any presupposed subject/object relation as a scientific imperative to objectivity. On the contrary, the researcher's intentions, cast in the object, are part of the object's identity⁶. Unpegged from any single disciplinary perspective, Generic Epistemology

6. Interestingly, Schmid et al. cite the example of NASA's exploration program on Mars and its deployment of robots

presupposes the creation of an “outside” space, a space structured by experiments in “inventive thinking which no longer treats objects as given and known” (Schmid 2013). According to Schmid, this outside space is striated by zones of inseparability and zones of incompleteness, “an immanent in-between” (*un mi-lieu immanent*) from which new interdisciplinary and ‘indisciplinary’ objects can be constructed. Generic Epistemology reclaims the act of scientific invention inspired by the emergence of complex computer simulations expressed in a variety of heterogeneous symbolic languages (i.e. pluriformalized modelizations) that can be found for example in the field of climate studies where multiple prismatic perspectives are needed to account for a research object composed of thousands of different models, incompatible scales, data collection practices and heterogeneous objects. Models, in their capacity to mediate between different ontologies, are understood as necessary buffer zones between theory and experience or between experience and fact. They offer a middle ground, where one can put in practice the displacement of continuities and oppositions between conflicting epistemological regimes. By establishing a democracy of disciplines, Generic Epistemology can address fragments and bodies of knowledge in a horizontal fashion, while remaining totally independent from the formation and the institution of these very same disciplines. Generic Epistemology introduces a new type of object that is not simply definitional but somehow operationalizes the discourse predicated on the fragmentary nature of knowledge production. *Integrative objects*, according to Schmid, are formed by the superposition of bodies of knowledges, disciplinary fragments, collective intelligences and individual researcher intentions. The comics industry, with its infrastructural backends, is an integrative object.

Distributed in multiple disciplinary levels, both in space and time, integrative objects consist of new types of contemporary objects that are convened in a non-conventional manner, counter to the phenomenological distance separating object and subject. According to researcher Patricia Reed, integrative objects “radically undo our conventional concept of ‘object-particulars’ [...] since these new objects are massively distributed in space (they are extra-local, and extra-disciplinary) and time (from the milliseconds of communication transactions to the long temporality of geological transformation in some cases)” (Reed 2016). Their understanding does not depend on any specific theory, any particular discipline nor any relation to the present state

of knowledge. Integrative objects form “a disciplinary hole” (*un trou disciplinaire*) (Schmid et al. 2011:21) that allows a displacement of disciplines to proceed by strategically locating zones of inseparability where different doctrinal regimes overlap. Through multiple partial approaches and non-convergent disciplinary perspectives, the goal of a research project is to always approach its object in an indirect way, in order to not reduce it to its most known elements, but instead to complexify it. In comics, this would be translated by the demotion of narratological devices and text-image correlationism in favor of new cartographies of knowledge where non-overlapping disciplinary fragments, hypotheses and other research ingredients are put into play in a rich cognitive setting. An example of coming from the introduction vignettes is quite telling in that regard. By framing comics through the lenses of what anthropologist Arjun Appadurai names “ex-commodities” (Appadurai 1986:16), defined as things retrieved temporarily or permanently from the commodity state, Inès Chuquet mobilizes physical evidence for establishing an industrial history of a medium, and forging new practices in collectability. In this regard, comics is an integrative object whose epistemological space needs to grant a status to an alien heterogeneity, as a fragile but necessary prerequisite for the formation of virtual and futural artistic practices.

As Schmid, Mambrini-Doudet and Hatchuel assert, it is a considerable challenge to organize the combination of knowledge from different disciplines in an agile way and without having to center any particular discipline. Existing classifications of interdisciplinarity present a diverse range of possible disciplinary relations in the articulation of the heterogeneous elements from each discipline. At times, combinatorial modes favour the juxtaposition of different knowledge(s), the integration of new insights, synthetic views of collective intelligence, or a more institutionalised “metaprogrammatic” perspective, with a political oriented goal to foster new expertise.

The authors advance a new hypothesis of non-continuity, where a combinatorial approach to knowledge is cut short. The goal is not to foster a common language in order to bridge the gap between different regimes of knowledge production, but to instead make of this gap the very same condition of working across disciplines. As they provocatively argue, incomprehension is much more productive than simili of common understanding, and researchers should not seek at all costs “to understand each other, not to project a meaning from one area to another, not to assume transparency of meanings, but to construct *iterations*” (my highlight) (Hatchuel et al. 2011). This last

term, emphasizes the authors' familiarity with modelization processes, as it is used in describing the iterative nature of training in neural networks.

Here, Schmid and Hatchuel introduce the practice of "fiction" as a multiplier of disciplinary perspectives, a way to alienate the object of research from a state of received knowledges and to open it up to an expanded cognitive field. Fiction is distinguished from invention, so far as it "assumes a point of externality" where the study of an object is disentangled from any specific discipline and irreducible to its most well-known concepts, but can still be constituted without these. Following Schmid's example of mathematics "without" numbers, philosophy "without" transcendental concepts and mechanics "without" authority, what would comics be "without" narratives or "without" images?

When comics are hollowed out from their main object of study, they reclaim the status of multidimensional entities; each discipline offering a partial perspective to the object becomes a dimension of it and contributes to the construction of an object. When readerly and writerly subjectivities that have dominated much of the critical discourse are purged from our understanding of comics, and when the established protocols or the best practices for conducting research are no longer provided, comics fail to "fall under one set of finalities" (Mackay 2012). Experimental or "advanced technologies" present exactly the same opportunity for Schmid's fiction as a productive method to comics futuralities. The following example, whose description should be quoted in its entirety, originates from the investment portfolio of a small organization based in Brussels. It manifests a sort of futurity where comics are no longer 'disciplined' and instead are considered through the lenses of financial speculation, not as the joyless accumulative practice in comics collectordom, but as an active productive force with radical imaginative capacity to construct alternative forms of media preservation.

"As the market for vintage and rare comics reaches astronomical prices, comics collectordom has its own mechanisms to assess the condition and value of a print. An entire industry-specific dictionary was put in place in order to mitigate the risks of investment. One can find a rich jargon of terms such as 'deacidification', 'oxidation shadow' and 'quinone stains'. Every wear and tear mark has a name. Every name reflects practices of mishandling. Every name represents a tangible asset liability. For comics collectors, whatever is outside a heavy duty 4-mil acid-free Mylar sleeve loses its

collector value. All this changed when **Echo Chamber**, a small organisation based in Brussels decides to address deterioration not as a logistical problem, but as an opportunity. The organisation's *Radical Conservation* portfolio targets wealthy collectors and offers a variety of derivatives for those that are willing to entrust them their valuable possessions. Their underlying business idea is that decay, an inevitable fate for paper products, can be programmed, even artificially accelerated in order to reflect the collector's idiosyncrasy. Some of the previous commissions include cases of expedited disintegration where *Bone's* first issue from a Dutch client was buried along long-term Organic Carbon sequestration in tidal marsh sediments along Scheldt's estuarine salinity gradients in Belgium, or a highly entropic environment where a mint copy of *Tales of Suspense #39* laid in monitored exposure to microbial deteriogens and macrofauna such as tubeworms and bivalves in the company's Pacific Lab." (Echo Chamber 2019)

The redefinition of comics research through the lenses of the financialization of decay for collectibles is not framed here as an enriched commentary, nor as a failure to mobilize popular concepts that can be found in Comics Studies, whether these are artistic, narrative or community specific. In the aforementioned case, we are presented with a speculative scenario of media disintegration, where the relation of comics media to geological time, the proceedings of an R&D experimental lab and the financial operations of trading, allow an estrangement of comics, distancing them from an accustomed position or set of popular associations that define academic research. By hollowing out comics from the dominant modes of knowledge production but also by the current state of knowledge, Schmid's and Hatchuel's fiction grants every piece of knowledge and every hypothesis, in the frame of the study, a relative consistency and autonomy.

On the contrary, the proposal mobilizes productive concepts that are situated in atypical areas of research in relation to Comics Studies, and ultimately contributes to the restoration of comics as an "unknown" object that can remain partly indeterminate and susceptible to virtual and future notions. The epistemological result, and here Schmid urges the reader to wager, is not the violent reconfiguration of knowledge production described by Kuhn's paradigm shifts, in a constant cycle of historical continuities. On the contrary, it's the formation of a site of interdisciplinarity, a space of superposed

methods, hypotheses, practices and theories, where knowledge is expanded through “collective intimacy” (Schmid and Hatchuel 2014:137). This reframing has an important epistemological impact on the way we engage with the comics industry as producers or consumers. Instead of displacing the medium’s conceptual scaffolding on certain assumptions of what craftsmanship, authorship or readership is, an understanding of comics as a technical/computational object through the operational intensity of its infrastructural backend provides a dynamic context that allows for new and diverse forms of media engagement, that are not conventionally understood as comics works.

As it can be intuited from the artistic components of this thesis, a conceptualisation of disciplinary concurrence has informed my understanding of artistic research in contemporary comics. From *Peanuts Minus Schulz* and its reflection on organization planning through globally distributed labor and *The Cubicle Island’s* human-algorithmic revisiting of press cartoons to *Compendium’s* semantic segmentation of proto-narrative elements, *Shapereader’s* index poetics through the lenses of disability studies and *Fastwalkers, the first comic book co-created with emergent AI, my artistic work demonstrates how a constructive approach to comics futurality is predicated on working across disciplines*. An investigative exploration of comics not only renegotiates the very concept of comics making, but also investigates the prospects of what can be done, both in theory and through practice, with a concept of comics not as a ‘thing’ with immutable structures, histories and affects but as an ongoing project, where new forms of intuition are put forward and new methodologies have to be devised according to their very specific needs. I’ve investigated the aforementioned concepts in various ways: through curatorial commissions, through writing, and through my publishing practice. This thesis argues for a novel comics praxeology informed by a rigorous disciplinary concurrence in comics research, and a heightened perceptual awareness of the comics industry’s very own infrastructural affordances.

Précis

This thesis is structured as follows:

In **Chapter 1**, I examine how the shortcomings of institutional representation in comics and the eroding role of the existing institutions in the increasingly interconnected, globalized comics industries might be conceived as both an invitation to formulate an alternative institutional memory, and as productive conditions for a contemporary comics praxeology.

In **Chapter 2**, I take a closer look at the composition process of the book *Abrégé de Bande Dessinée Franco-Belge*. I examine how the book was built following the precepts of ontography's model of conceptual representation of objects, focusing on the rich visual typology of graphemes drawn from the Franco-Belgian tradition of the bande dessinée.

Chapter 3 consists of two parts that focus on the project Shapereader, a system specifically designed for users with visual impairment with regards to the production and consumption of tactile comics. The first part is a theoretical investigation of the tactile novel *Arctic Circle*, and explores some of the strategies used to translate concepts and elementary semantic features into haptic formations. The second part consists of the artist notes as well as various exploratory tangents related to embodied cognition and includes a visual documentation of the multiple forms of engagement that occurred around the project over the last few years.

In **Chapter 4**, I reflect on my conceptual comic book *Peanuts Minus Schulz* and how distributed digital labor, used as an opaque, material and possibly disruptive compositional practice redefines the contemporary disenchantment in digital comics with information flows, and rethinks the industrial precepts of the medium in post-digital production modes.

Chapter 5 is a technical paper sketching how a production pipeline based on deep learning technologies such as computer vision algorithms, language modelling for text generation and image generation algorithms, can be used for the production of an entire synthetic comics book.

Chapter 6 is a multicomponent chapter that brings together four short articles that explore the unconventional work from individual conceptual comics artists and establishes the

conditions for affective lineages among similarly minded practitioners in comics.

Comics

This section collates my artistic research that was mostly manifested through the form of books published under different imprints and with the help of various of partnering institutions.

Abrégé de Bande Dessinée Franco-Belge, published in 2018, is presented as a non-exhaustive idiosyncratic index of elements considered to generally define the tradition of Franco-Belgian comics. *Abrégé* is structured as an orchestral comic book whose elements such as comics proto-memes, metanarrative devices and paratextual elements, once extracted by their original books and freed from the imperatives of their specific narratives can be contemplated as the building blocks of the European BD.

The Cubicle Island was published in 2020. It is a conceptual comic book project that explores the blurring between human and machinic subjectivities through the distributed ramifications of digital labor and the new regimes of work and playbor in the making of an international class of precarious cognitive workers. It collects hundreds of desert island cartoons, a genre that reached its peak of popularity in 1957, possibly as an expression of a Cold War fear of the nuclear bomb and the nascent alienation felt by the increasing post-fordist labor regimes. The cartoons were then outsourced to digital labor farms, where an unskilled textual labor force (microworkers) and different algorithmic surrogates (process of offices automation) were solicited to contribute to the book by proposing punchlines for each cartoon.

Peanuts Minus Schulz appeared in 2021 and consists of the reproduction of Charles Schulz's work by commissioned artists, using digital tools and mediated by a digital labor management platform. The book explores the industrial affordances of comics and proposes an alternative production belt, where the differences between contributors are neither levelled nor neutralized. Contrarily to mainstream comics, the book is composed from a diversity of temperamental and idiosyncratic approaches to the interpretation of Schulz's work. *Peanuts Minus Schulz* underlines the very nature of comics as an eternal score subjected to vagaries and contextual instantiations.

Fastwalkers is the first synthetic comic book generated with emergent AI. Co-created with emergent AI (GAN, GPT-3), and developed by an interdisciplinary team of

computer scientists and designers, the book is the eclectic outgrowth of a variety of different indexing regimes, community datasets, proprietary algorithms, beta-testing and generative models trained on millions of data units and bodies of text. By addressing the aggregate nature of knowledge production in the semiocapitalist age, *Fastwalkers* thematizes the inherent computational qualities of comics and operates a foray in the latent space lurking in the reader's pre-attentive cognition.

Lastly, *The Neural Yorker* is an AI engine that posts synthetic cartoons on Twitter. It is based on a GAN-derived model and a pre-trained GPT-2 transformer trained on millions of data units whose collection occurred on a variety of different indexing regimes and systems of classification and labelling. The multitude of epistemic regimes is not only thematized here as a metaphor or a theoretical perspective on the increasingly aggregate nature of knowledge production in our computational age, but becomes an operational procedure in the construction of the very same synthetic cartoons.

Curatorial work

In October 2020, I was invited to curate a *Conceptual Comics Archive* for the online media collections Ubuweb and Monoskop, popularly known as 'shadow libraries'. The collections feature seventy-five books and other printed formats that have been documented, and photographed from cover to cover, with a focus on the materiality of the artefacts. Each document is presented along with metadata and a text from the publisher's press release or a small critical introduction to the work written in order to provide background information about the needs of the collection. The collection embraces equally real, unclaimed, anticipated and fictional practices in their perpetual materialisation. As a whole, it reflects on the specific sites of production and their potential to register meaning and organise discourse based on inscriptions of the material language of the industry.

Shadow Libraries: Ubuweb in Athens was a three-day festival at the Onassis Cultural Centre in Athens that I co-curated with Kenneth Goldsmith. The program consisted of an exhibition, an educational program of four workshops and two symposia and explored the conceptual consistency and the ethics of digital preservation and distribution from the practitioners' perspective. The invited guests unpacked the 'thingness' of these fragile knowledge infrastructures and discussed how their architecture challenges current norms of intellectual property rights, market concentration and control of access.

The Futures of Comics is an international non-academic research programme that explores how comics are undergoing historic mutations in the midst of increasingly financialized, globalized technological affordances and proposes to map the social, economic, racial and gendered forces that shape the industry's commercial, communication and production routines. Through reading sessions, artist talks, various workshops open to the general public, a symposium and the production of a temporary library / reading space, Futures of Comics attempted to document and reflect on contemporary artistic practices with the goal of providing a resonating chamber for works and practices that are little known outside of comics communities.

Lastly, ***The Mural*** explores Shapereader and its tactile resources as a speculative tool of graphic musical notation. The work was installed in the Balzaal of the Kunstencentrum Vooruit, in Spring 2020 and in the middle of the global pandemic. In compliance with Belgian health regulations, this art residency was an opportunity to invite eighteen performers from a variety of musical backgrounds on a daily basis. Structured as individual meetings, we discussed and shared affective (and other pre-attentive) individual experiences related to embodied experiences in sound production, and together conceptualized the building blocks for a tactile, graphic musical notation according to each performer's preoccupations. During the month of April 2021, and along with the different participants, we questioned the normativity of conventional notation tools, discussed the de-emphasizing of vision with regards to "reading" music and explored the manifold ways in which sound can be translated and stimulated by touch. The encounters, the short performances and the interviews with musicians were documented on camera, and were released as a short film - a collective commemoration on the awareness of mutuality in the sense of touch, that may never be the same again.

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This thesis embraces an attitude of productive estrangement towards the medium's forms, material qualities and operations, and constructs comics as a "contemporary object". Understanding such an object depends on the increasingly aggregate nature of knowledge production and dissemination in the computational age. Both in theory, with a series of papers in peer-review journals, and in artistic practice, by way of published comics and commissioned curatorial projects, this thesis examines the mutations of the comics ecology as an expansion of the scope of knowledge. It embraces the cumulative impact of digital transformation and articulates a novel comics praxeology predicated on two conditions. First, the thesis appeals for a systematic exploration of comics outside of narrow media purviews, the implicitly disciplinary conceptions, and the dominant historical perspectives in Comics Studies. It aims to develop a conception that embraces a rigorous application of a non-hegemonic interdisciplinarity in comics research. Second, and most importantly, the thesis argues for the expansion of operational agency on the part of comics professionals. This agency is described as a heightened contextual appreciation of the industry's infrastructural backend, an awareness of its imbricated institutions and a diversification of the professional toolbox. I argue that a novel comics praxeology is a necessary attribute in order to embrace future, speculative, unclaimed or hitherto impossible forms in comics expression.

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